

Answers for Correlation between liver cancer and tobacco usage in Alabama 2000-2010

General

Topic

What is the main research question of the project?

is there a relationship between tobacco usage and liver cancer incidence

Please give some keywords describing the research question.

- tobacco usage
- tobacco
- cancer
- USA
- liver cancer
- Alabama
- 2000-2010
- smoking
- smoker
- liver
-

Research field

Which research field(s) does this project belong to?

- Life Sciences / Basic Biological and Medical Research
- Life Sciences / Medicine

Which persons or institutions are responsible for the project coordination?

- khaled maher awad

Project schedule

When does the project start?

March 20, 2019

When does the project end?

June 30, 2019

Project coordination

Which persons or institutions are responsible for the project coordination?

- khaled maher awad

Other requirements I

Are there requirements regarding the data management from other parties (e.g. the scholarly/scientific community)?

No

Content classification

What kind of dataset is it?

Tobacco Usage: this dataset used to describe the ratio of tobacco users in USA states at each year in the period of 1995-2010 and this dataset contain the following information (state : String , Year : int64 , Smoking everyday : String , Smoking sometimes : String , Never smoked : String)

Liver Cancer Incidence: this dataset used to describe the number of (liver , lunge and Bronchus , Tongue , mouth) cancer incidence in USA states at each year in the period of 2000 - 2015 and this dataset contain the following information (state : String , Year : int64 , cancer Site: String , Age : String , Sex : String , Sex code : String , Count : int64)

Final Dataset: this dataset used to describe the relationship between tobacco usage and number of liver cancer incidence in alabama state in USA at the period 2000-2010 and the dataset contain the following data (State : String , Year : int64 , num of liverCancerIncidence : int64 , num of TobaccoUser : int64)

Is the dataset being created or re-used?

Tobacco Usage: Re-used

Liver Cancer Incidence: Re-used

Final Dataset: Created

If re-used, who created the dataset?

Tobacco Usage: Centers for Disease Control and PreventionCenters for Disease Control and Prevention Kaggle team chris Crawford sohier Dane Noah Daniels Jessica lie paul Mooney

Liver Cancer Incidence: The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention National Program of Cancer Registries (NPCR) The National Cancer Institute Surveillance, Epidemiology and End Results (SEER) program

Final Dataset: -

If re-used, under which address, PID or URL can the dataset be found?

Tobacco Usage: <https://www.kaggle.com/cdc/tobacco-use>

Liver Cancer Incidence: <https://wonder.cdc.gov/cancer.html>

Final Dataset: -

Which individuals, groups or institutions could be interested in re-using this dataset? What are possible scenarios?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: the data will be useful to the tobacco users to help him to get rid of this bad habit and it may be useful as a reference for Cancer protection societies, social institutions that treat addiction, hospitals and other students.

Is the dataset reproducible in the sense that it could be created / collected anew in case it got lost?

Tobacco Usage: yes, with moderate, but reasonable effort

Liver Cancer Incidence: yes, with moderate, but reasonable effort

Final Dataset: yes, with moderate, but reasonable effort

Technical classification

When does data collection or creation start?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: March 20, 2019

When does data collection or creation end?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: April 1, 2019

When does data cleansing / data preparation start?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: April 1, 2019

When does data cleansing / data preparation end?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: April 3, 2019

When does data analysis start?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: April 4, 2019

When does data analysis end?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: April 10, 2019

What is the actual or expected size of the dataset?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: exact size: 371 BYTE

How much data is produced per year?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: -

Which file formats are used?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: csv

Which tools, software, technologies or processes are used to generate or collect the data?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: we used python programming language and we used pandas and matplotlib library

Which software, processes or technologies are necessary to use the data?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: all you need is csv viewer

Is documentation about relevant software needed to use the data?

Tobacco Usage: No

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: No

Are different versions of the dataset created?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: No

Which versioning strategy is applied for this dataset?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: after the first publication of the dataset , the users comments and reviews will be taken on account to enhance the dataset and doing deeper research to satisfy them and all the changes that would be applied in the first version should not take more than 3 months , after the second version it would a monthly review from the author

Which technology or tool is used for versioning?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: Not yet decided

Data usage

How / for what purpose will this dataset be used during the project?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: Most people think that cigarettes have an effect on the heart and on the lung only, but many of us do not know how every cigarette smoked by humans affects the liver. Tobacco products in all its forms have a severe effect on the liver. This is because the toxins that are abundant in tobacco products cause inflammation. And chronic signs in the liver, these infections in turn increase the susceptibility to liver cancer so the purpose of collecting this data to help smokers to get rid of these bad habit

How often will this dataset be used?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: all time , whenever you want

To what extent will infrastructure resources be required (e.g. CPU hours, bandwidth, storage space... etc.).

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: Infrastructure resources of the usual workplace equipment are sufficient.

Are there actual or potential usage scenarios that could benefit from support by a data management or IT expert, or that even require such support?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: No

Where is the dataset stored during the project?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: the data is in the folder /SW_Exercise/Raw datasets/Tobacco Usage.csv & /SW_Exercise/Raw datasets/Liver Cancer Incidence.csv , the resulted file is in the folder /SW_Exercise/Transformed datasets/transformed.csv

Under which URL can the dataset be accessed during the project?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: github : https://github.com/KhaledMaher024/SW_Exercise zenodo : <https://zenodo.org/record/2642043#.X>

Are there internal project guidelines for a consistent organisation of the data? If so, where they are documented?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: Not yet

Is there a internal project guideline for naming the data? If so, please briefly outline the naming conventions and, if necessary, link to the documentation.

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: Yes: the resulted data will contain the following data (state , year , number of smoker , number of livercancer incidence) in csv format

Who is allowed to access the dataset?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: all the people are allowed to access the dataset

How and how often will backups of the data be created?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: the data backup is created by zenodo website and GitHub (in which the data is uploaded on them) by themselves they provide this service

Who is responsible for the backups?

Tobacco Usage:</>

-

Liver Cancer Incidence:

-

Final Dataset:

- zenedo
- github

Which measures or provisions are in place to ensure data security (e.g. protection against unauthorized access, data recovery, transfer of sensitive data)?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: the data is stored in safe repository in github website and also uploaded in Zenedo and i put a username and password so can nobody can access it until ending the research except the author but after first publication anyone can use the data and share it and edit it in other aspects, we prevent data loss by weekly data backup that is free for 28 days and after that it will cost money by barrcouda also we created a DOI for the resulted data that identify the dataset from other dataset and its : 10.1234/khaled.maher

Is this dataset interoperable, i.e. allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries etc.?

Final Dataset:

- The dataset adheres to standardised formats: csv
- The dataset is usable with available (open) software applications or software applications that are established and widely used in the respective community: python
- The dataset can easily be re-combined with different datasets from different origins

Will this dataset be published or shared?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: Yes, internally with everyone, as long as they don't pass on the data

If no, please explain why not. Please differentiate between legal and contractual reasons and voluntary restrictions.

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset:

If yes, under which terms of use or license will the dataset be published or shared?

Final Dataset:

- Attribution (BY)
- Public domain (CC0)

If there are any restrictions on the re-use of this dataset, please explain why.

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: before the final version of the dataset there is no restriction on using the data and accessing it or editing it all this because the researcher who wants to use the data and update it that's will help us to make or include a bigger number of researchs but after the final version the dataset is allowed to be accessed and used but cannot edit it

When will the data be published (if they are)?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: June 30, 2019

Will the data be collaboratively used?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: No

Which platform / tools is / are used for collaboratively working on data and publications?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: python

How is the collaborative work on the same files organised?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset:

Which measures of quality assurance are taken for this dataset?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: there is some of method that used in original datasets to produce the final dataset 1.remove all the rows that are no in the specified period from the 2 dataset 2.remove all the rows that are not in the Alabama state 3.remove the percentage of "Never smoked" coulumn and change its type 4.calculate the number of smoker for each year by substracting 1 by the value of "Never smoked" column 5.group by the 2 dataset by the year and state column each individually 6.merge the 2 processed dataset to one dataset " final dataset " 7.check the null fields and fill it by the median value the final dataset will contain (state , year , # liver cancer incidence , # smoker , cancer site)

Data integration

Is the integration between the re-used and newly created data ensured? If yes, by which means?

Costs

What are the personnel costs for data management associated with the creation or acquisition of data in the project?

0 PM

What is the amount of non-personnel-costs for data management associated with the creation or acquisition of data in the project?

0.0 Euro

What are the personnel costs for data management associated with the the usage of data in the project?

0 PM

What is the amount of non-personnel-costs for data management associated with the usage of data in the project?

0.0 Euro

What are the personnel costs associated with data storage and data security in the project?

0 PM

What is the amount of non-personnel costs associated with the storage of the data sets during the project?

0.0 Euro

Metadata and referencing

Which information is necessary for other parties to understand the data (that is, to understand their collection or creation, analysis, and research results obtained on its basis) and to re-use it?

Final Dataset:</>

- Time
- Identifiers
- Other: Counts

Which standards, ontologies, classifications etc. are used to describe the data and context information?

Final Dataset:</>

- It has not yet been decided, with which system the metadata and contextual information will be described

Which metadata are collected automatically?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: -

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: Yes

Which metadata are collected semi-automatically?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: -

Which metadata are collected manually?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: The metadata file can be found inside the project folder (/documentation/metadata.xml). the metadata will provide some information to help the users or other people to discover the purpose for this dataset like : subject , title , language , description , type , format and other information another documentation are used to help on discoverability is documentation.txt is found on the folder (/documentation/documentation.txt) that give a brief on the purpose of this dataset

Are metadata and context information being checked for correctness and completeness?

Final Dataset:</>

- Manual check for completeness

Who is responsible for documenting the metadata and context information and for checking if they are correct and complete?

Tobacco Usage:</>

-

Liver Cancer Incidence:</>

-

Final Dataset:</>

- khaled maher awad

Metadata costs

What are the personnel costs associated with the the creation of metadata and context information in the project?

0 PM

What is the amount of non-personnel-costs associated with the creation of metadata and context information in the project?

0.0 Euro

What is the structure of the data? How are the individual components of the dataset related to each other? How is the dataset related to other datasets used in the project?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: the resulted data will contain the following data (state , year , number of smoker , number of livercancer incidence) in csv format the relationship between increasing the percentage of smoking and the proportion of liver cancer and drawing results in easy-to-understand charts contribute significantly to increasing people's awareness about the seriousness of smoking and harmful, which gives the opportunity for smokers to think about quitting smoking and maintaining a healthy body of diseases

Will persistent identifiers (PIDs) be used for this data set?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: Yes

Which system of persistent identifiers shall be used?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: Other: DOI

Which (sub-) entities / sub units should be referenced using identifiers? Which of those identifiers should be persistent and citable?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset:

Who is responsible for the maintenance of the PIDs and the object maintenance (i.e. who is responsible notifying the PID-Service about object relocation and the new address)?

Tobacco Usage:</>

•

Liver Cancer Incidence:</>

-

Final Dataset:</>

- Khaled maher awad

PIDs costs

What are the personnel costs associated with of persistent identifiers in the project?

0 PM

What is the amount of non-personnel-costs associated with persistent identifiers in the project?

0.0 Euro

Legal and ethics

General legal issues

Does the legal situation of different countries have to be considered?

No

Does this dataset contain personal data?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: No

Does this dataset contain sensitive data other than personal data?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: No

If yes, please describe the non-personal sensitive data used in the project.

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset:

Does the funder have rules or recommendations for data management? If yes, please briefly outline them and refer to more detailed sources of information if necessary. Please also indicate, if the rules / guidelines are mandatory or optional.

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: no

Official approval

Has the project been approved by a research ethics committee?

Not yet, it will be handed in for review by

Is a statutory approval / permit needed for the research?

No

If yes, which permit?

If yes, which is the responsible agency?

Is a data access committee needed to handle access requests to the published data of the project?

No

Intellectual property rights I

Does the project use and/or produce data that is protected by intellectual or industrial property rights?

Yes

Does copyright law apply to this dataset?

Final Dataset:</>

- No

Do other intellectual property rights apply to this dataset?

Final Dataset:</>

- No

Was investigated who the rights owner is?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset:

Intellectual property rights costs

What are the personnel costs associated with intellectual property rights in the project?

0 PM

What is the amount of non-personnel-costs regarding intellectual property rights in the project?

0.0 Euro

Storage and long-term preservation

Selection

What are the criteria / rules for the selection of the data to be archived (after the end of the project)?

the data that is wanted to be shared for long time is the final / resulted data that include the state name , the year , number of smoker , number of liver cancer incidence and these data is available as csv file , the data has no specified time to be stored in the repository the persistent identifier for the data is : 10.1234/khaled.maher

Who selects the data to be archived?

- khaled maher awad

Does this dataset have to preserved for the long-term?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: Yes

What are the reasons this dataset has to be preserved for the long-term?

Final Dataset:</>

- Used in a publication / proof of good scientific practice

How long will the data be stored?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: 2 years or 3 years

How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable.

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: untill the final version of the dataset

Where will the data (including metadata, documentation and, if applicable, relevant code) be stored or archived after the end of the project?

Final Dataset:</>

- Generic data center: Github or Zenedo

Is the repository or data centre chosen certified (e.g. Data Seal of Approval, nestor Seal or ISO 16363)? (If the dataset is archived at several places, you may answer this question with yes, if this applies to at least one of these.)

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: Yes

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: Yes

Shall there be an embargo period before the data are made available?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: there is no data embargo on the resulted data , the produced data can be used by students or another researcher in thier researchs , the produced data has no personal data or sensitive data so there is no restricted data.

How will the identity of the person accessing the data will be ascertained?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: ——

By when will the data be archived?

Tobacco Usage:

Liver Cancer Incidence:

Final Dataset: April 22, 2019

Long-term preservation costs

What are the personnel costs associated with long-term preservation for the project?

0 PM

How will the datamanagement costs of the project be covered?

there is no cost for data management so far

What is the amount of non-personnel-costs regarding long-term preservation for the project?

0.0 Euro